

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HUMAN RESOURCE AND
SUSTAINABILITY OF FREE DAY SECONDARY EDUCATION;
A SURVEY OF IMENTI NORTH SUB-COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

This study aimed at establishing the relationship between Human resource and sustainability of public day secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County. The study had the following objectives; the influence of salary, management leadership, incentives, training and development and their relationship with sustainability of public day secondary schools in Kenya. This study sought to test the hypothesis that; salary, management leadership, incentives, training and development affect sustainability of free day secondary schools. The study adopted descriptive and explorative research design since its main aim is to explain human resource variables that affect sustainability of public day secondary schools in Kenya. The target population was 29 public day secondary schools in Imenti North sub-County. The respondents were selected using stratified random sampling to identify sample schools and simple random sampling to select respondents from the identified strata. The sample respondents comprised of 12 principals, 61 HODs and 136 teachers totaling 173 respondents. Data was collected using structured open ended, closed ended and unstructured questionnaire. Reliability was tested by test-retest method using Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient which was used to test the correlations between the items. Correlation coefficient of above 0.7 was obtained and was deemed acceptable for the study. Data was analyzed by use of descriptive statistics and logistic regression. Descriptive statistics and multiple logistic regression was used to test the cause and effect relationship between the dependent and independent variables under the study.

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All the hypothesis was tested at 5% level of significance or 95% confidence level. The analyzed data is presented in frequency tables, pie charts and bar graphs. It is expected that the results of the study will assist education stakeholders and the Ministry of education to address human resource challenges that affect sustainability of public day secondary schools in Kenya.

JEL: J24, O15, H75, I25

Keywords: relationship, human resource, free day secondary education

1. Introduction

It is acknowledged worldwide that the most important resource for social economic development of any nation is its human resource (Gary, 2005). This is the main reason why individuals, organizations and nations invest heavily in human resource development (Scott, 2007). Human resource is the most important asset a company has and good human resource delivers in terms of organizational performance (Boxall and Parcell, 2003). HRM is not only critical in Organization performance but is also much more important than an emphasis on quality, competitive strategy, quality, research and design (R&D) in terms of influence of the bottom line (Stredwick, 2005). Human capital (Resource) can be defined as people and the time, personnel skills, capabilities, experiences and knowledge they bring to their work. Human capital is obtained through a variety of means which includes formal education, job training, on the job learning and life experiences (Derrick, 2005). Globally HR managers are faced with the dilemma of how to manage their employees from global perspective. International trade is at an all new level, resulting in a highly globalized business (Gordad, 2004). Hence, constant changes in how organizations employ and manage human talent require practices and systems that are well conceived and effectively implemented to ensure high performance and continuous success. The need to develop a global perspective on human resource management (HRM) has been part of the managerial landscape for a while now (Lewin, 2007).

2. Statement of the problem

The large number of enrolment of students in Kenyan free day secondary schools confirms how desperate poor Kenyans were to have their children acquire secondary education (MoEST, 2009). Students enrollment in day secondary schools has increased

yet the government has not equipped the schools with enough human resource to ensure students get good quality education like their counterparts in public boarding schools. A long standing shortage of teachers currently at 80,000 in Primary and post primary institutions and support staff is a key obstacle to the sustainability of free day secondary education in Kenya .The Ministry of education is currently employing the teachers to replace those who left the service through retirement, resignation or natural attrition (MoEST, 2015). This indicates that day schools will have to wait longer because the government has not employed enough teachers to teach students enrolling in Day secondary schools yet 65% of students in secondary are in day secondary schools (MoEST, 2015). Although the government is committed to providing free day secondary education, to achieve Education for All (EFA), there is little that is being done to achieve this target. Lack of adequate human resource in day secondary schools in Kenya has been the biggest hindrance in the sustainability of this noble programme (World Bank, 2008). Although increasing enrolment and ensuring every child has a right to education is desirable ,tight budgetary constraints often force poor countries to choose between providing quantity in education before improving its quality. However, achieving desirable level of enrolment without providing learners with adequate teachers may not be meaningful (Shaun, 2006).The quality of education offered in day secondary schools has been questioned. The lack of enough teachers is among the factors cited for the poor quality of education offered in day secondary schools (Abagi, 2009). Education sector has registered significant growth over the years, the number of Early childhood development centers (ECDE) ,primary and secondary education have increasedby16.9% between 2009-2014,with secondary school recording the highest growth rate at 8.2% (UNICEF, 2014). While this looks promising, nationally a lot of disparity exists in day schools in terms of qualified teaching personnel.

3. Specific Objectives

The study had the following specific objectives;

1. To determine the relationship between salary and sustainability of free day secondary education in Kenya.
2. To establish the relationship between management leadership and sustainability of free day secondary schools.
3. To investigate the relationship between incentives and sustainability of public free day secondary schools in Kenya.
4. To determine the relationship between training and development and sustainability of free day secondary education in Kenya.

3.1 Research Hypothesis

The study is guided by the following hypotheses;

H1: There is statistically significant positive relationship between Salary and sustainability of free day secondary education in Kenya.

H2: There is statistically significant positive relationship between Management leadership style and sustainability of day secondary schools in Kenya.

H3: There is statistically significant positive relationship between Incentives and sustainability of public day secondary schools in Kenya.

H4: There is statistically significant positive relationship between training and development and sustainability of free day secondary education in Kenya.

4. Theoretical Review

4.1 Herzberg Two Factor Theory

Herzberg two factor theory was developed by Fredrick Herzberg in 1959. Herzberg developed a theory of workplace motivation called the two-factor theory. The two-factor theory is based on the assumption that there are two sets of factors that influence employee's motivation in the workplace by either enhancing employee satisfaction or hindering it (Herzberg, 1959). The first of the two are called hygiene factors. Rather, Herzberg used the term 'hygiene' to describe factors that cause dissatisfaction in the workplace, are extrinsic (or independent of the work itself), and are linked to things such as compensation, job security, organizational politics, working conditions, quality of leadership, and relationships between supervisors, subordinates, and peers (Herzberg,1966).

According to Herzberg, these factors do not motivate employees. However, when they are missing or inadequate, hygiene factors can cause serious dissatisfaction. Feelings like being unhappy when you are be in a job where you were underpaid, being in fear of losing a job, dealing constantly with gossip, lacking effective leadership, and being surrounded by coworkers whom you despised (Herzberg,1968). Hygiene factors are all about making an employee feel comfortable, secure, and happy. When hygiene factors are not fulfilled, it feels like something is missing or not quite right (Herzberg, 1964).

The second factor is motivators or satisfiers. These are linked to [employee motivation](#) and arise from intrinsic, or dependent, conditions of the job itself. Factors for satisfaction include responsibility, job satisfaction, recognition, achievement, opportunities for growth, and advancement (Nathan, 1970). This theory suggests that to improve job attitudes and productivity, administrators must recognize and attend to

both sets of characteristics and not assume that an increase in satisfaction leads to decrease in unpleasable dissatisfaction (Hyun, 2009). This theory was found to be in agreement with salary as a factor that affects motivation

4.2 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a model of presentation where a researcher represents the relationship between the variables in the study base on three needs theory. The study proposes the following conceptual framework.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

5. Research Design and Methodology

This study was conducted through descriptive and explorative research design. Descriptive is a research design where information is collected without manipulating the environment, it provides information about naturally occurring behavior, attitudes and other characteristics of interest of a particular group. The target population for the study is 306 teachers in public day secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County of Meru County. Imenti North has 29 public day secondary schools. The target population will consist of Principals, HOD and ordinary teachers in these day secondary schools.

Secondary education is critical in the whole of education system in Kenya. Secondary education is a precursor for post-secondary education and training. The availability of well trained and qualified teachers is crucial to sustainability of day secondary education.

The study employed Stratified sampling and simple random sampling to select the sample. Stratified sampling was used to identify strata in the population and their proportion and then use simple random sampling to obtain a sample from each strata, (Sakran, 2003). The sample size for the study was determined using the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + n * e^2}$$

Where

n = the desired sample size for the study

N = the target population

E = level of significance for the study

e = 0.05 or 5%

$$n = \frac{306}{1 + 306 * 0.05^2} = 173 \text{ Respondents}$$

It is on the basis of stratified and simple random sampling that 221 respondents have been selected for this study. The sample constituted 57 % of the target population. Questionnaire was the main tool for collecting data for the study. The data was collected using well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics are used to describe the basic features of the data in a study. They provide simple summary about the sample and their measures. Logistic regression was used to analyze the data. Logistic regression tests the relationship between the categorical dependent variable and the independent variables. The model is expressed mathematically as:

$$f(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

Where $Z = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4$

The hypothesis of the study was tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) the data was analyzed at 5% level of significance because it is the most commonly used value. Analyzed data is presented in tables, charts and graphs.

6. Data Analysis, Presentation and Interpretation

A total of 173 questionnaires were distributed to the teachers in public day secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County. Of the 173 questionnaires sent to respondents, 154 were returned for analysis representing a response rate of 89% which is statistically acceptable. According to Mugenda (2003), a return of above 50% of the questionnaires is acceptable.

This section presents data on relationship between salary and sustainability of public day secondary schools, the relationship between management leadership and sustainability, the relationship between incentives and sustainability and finally the training and development and sustainability of public day secondary schools. This was presented as below;

Table 1: Teachers are well remunerated by their employer

Teachers are well remunerated by their employer	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	21	13.6
Disagree	133	86.4
Total	154	100

The researcher sought the opinion of the teachers whether they are well remunerated by their employer the TSC. A whopping 76.9% of the teachers disagreed while 13.6% agreed that teachers are well paid. The results indicate that teachers are not comfortable with their earnings.

Table 2: Teachers are well remunerated by their employer

School has BOM employed teachers	Frequency	Percent
Agree	150	97.4
Disagree	2	1.3
Total	154	100

The respondents were asked to state whether their schools have employed BoM teachers to fill the gaps. A majority 97.4% of the respondents agreed while 2.6% disagreed. The results indicates the almost all the day schools in Imenti North Sub-County are understaffed and this could be compromising the quality of education offered in day schools compromising their quality and hence their sustainability. This is because no parent wants to send their children in understaffed schools.

Table 3: BoM teachers constantly change working stations

BoM teachers constantly change working stations	Frequency	Percent
Agree	128	83.2
Disagree	26	16.8
Total	154	100

The respondents were asked whether teachers employed by the BoM keep on changing working stations. A majority of the respondents 83.2% agreed while 15.6% disagreed. The results indicate there is high turnover of BoM teachers with most of them moving to better paying schools especially boarding schools that are well endowed with resources and this compromises learning with constant change of instructors.

Table 4: Effective BoM in your school

You have effective BoM in your school	Frequency	Percent
Agree	144	93.5
Disagree	10	6.5
Total	154	100

From the table, it was established that almost all public day secondary schools had effective board of management with 93.5% agreeing while only a paltry 6.5% holding a contrary opinion.

Table 5: BoM holds meeting regularly

BoM holds meeting regularly	Frequency	Percent
Agree	114	74
Disagree	40	26
Total	154	100.0

Regarding whether The BoM holds meeting with the members of the teaching staff, 74% agreed while 26% disagreed. The results show that most day schools have effective BoM that consult teachers in decision making matters.

Table 6: There is performance based reward policy

There is performance based reward policy	Frequency	Percent
Agree	68	44.2
Disagree	86	55.8
Total	154	100

As shown, it was established that most day schools do not have performance based incentive policy with 55.8% expressing positive opinion and 42.2% disagreeing.

Table 7: Rewards plays a key role in retention of teachers in schools

Rewards plays a key role in retention of teachers in schools	Frequency	Percent
Agree	116	75.3
Disagree	38	24.7
Total	154	100

On whether incentive policy is motivating 55.8% disagreed while 44.2% agreed. Asked whether incentive policy plays a role in retention of teachers a whopping 75.3% agreed.

Table 8: Teachers need to undergo constant training

Teachers need to undergo constant training	Frequency	Percent
Agree	128	83.1
Disagree	26	16.9
Total	154	100

Majority of the teachers at 83.1% agreed there is need for teachers to undergo constant training while 16.9% held a contrary opinion.

Table 9: Teachers are regularly updated through seminars

Teachers are regularly updated through seminars	Frequency	Percent
Agree	58	37.7
Disagree	96	62.3
Total	154	100

A whopping 62.3% and respectively disagreed with 37.7% agreeing. The findings indicate that most teachers do not update their skills to cope with the competitive world of change. According to Weil and Woodall (2005), training and development is used to close the gap between the current performance and future performance in organizations.

Table 10: Training methods undergone helps improve your skills

Training methods undergone helps improve your skills	Frequency	Percent
Agree	128	83.1
Disagree	26	16.9
Total	154	100

A whopping 83.1% agreed with 16.9% expressing contrary opinion. The results indicate the need for regular training of employees irrespective of the organization they work for. The findings are in agreement with Armstrong (2009), who argues that organizations benefits from training and development through winning the hearts and the minds of the employees to align them with the organization and remain in the organization.

6.1 Logistic Regression

To determine the factors significantly associated with sustainability of public day secondary schools, logistic regression was utilized since the dependent variable was dichotomous. Logistic regression also termed logic model used in statistics is a regression model used when the dependent variable is categorical. Logistic regression measures the relationship between the categorical dependent variable and independent variables by estimating probabilities using logistic function. Logistic regression was chosen for the study because the dependent variable is categorical i.e. sustainable or not sustainable.

Table 11: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	416.804	4	104.144	28.144	.000
	Residual	540.547	146	3.702		
	Total	957.351	150			

Source: Researcher (2017)

The F ratio in ANOVA table test whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data .The table shows that the independent variables are statistically significant and predict the dependent variable, $(4,103) = 23.418, p < .005$. Hence, this indicate the regression model is a good fit for the data. Therefore, we accept the directional hypothesis that there is relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable sustainability. We support the research hypothesis that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

6.2 Model Summary

The summary of the model is illustrated in following table:

Table 13: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson
1	.660	.435	.420	1.92416	2.415

The logistic regression tests the relationship between the set of independent variables and the dependent variable. The R represents the multiple correlation coefficient which is 0.660. R is a measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable. In this case, 66% indicates a good level of prediction. R² is the coefficient of determination which is the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. This technically means it is the proportion of the variation accounted for by the regression model. This means the independent variable explain 42% of the variation. Hence, this is a good model. Adjusted R² corrects for multiple predictors, giving a slightly lower value of 42%.

6.3 Logistic Regression Coefficient

The logistic regression coefficient indicates the direction and strength of the relationship between the independent and dependent variable. It represents the influence of a one unit change in the independent variable on the log – odds of the dependent variable. Exp (β) is the exponentiation of the β coefficient which is an odds ratio. Odds describe the ratio of the number of occurrence to the number of non-occurrences. It has some relationship with probability since probability is the ratio of the number of occurrences to the total number of probabilities. Probability ranges from 0 to 1 whereas odds range from 0 to infinity (Hosmer and Lemeshow, 2000).

It is hence possible to convert findings to probability when they are reported as odds. Odds of one indicate equal probability of occurrence and non-occurrence. An odds less than one indicates that occurrence is less likely than non-occurrence. Odds greater than one indicates that occurrence is more likely than non-occurrence. Hence, Exp (B) indicates how many times higher the odds of occurrence are for each one unit increase in the independent variable. The results of the regression coefficients is illustrated below

Table 14: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	-4.686	1.843		-2.543	.012
Salary	.201	0.037	.353	5.440	.000
Management	.098	0.025	.327	3.952	.000
Incentives	.077	0.037	.174	2.103	.037
Training & Development	.025	0.040	.043	.629	.530

Source: Researcher (2017)

The findings shows that salary is significantly associated with sustainability of public day secondary schools with $p = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05 the significance level. The results show that an increase in one unit of salary increases the log odds of sustainability by 0.201. This is in line with a study by Wanyonyi (2004), who established that salary and other socio economic factors influence sustainability of free education in Kenya.

Management leadership was also found to be significantly associated with sustainability of day secondary education with log odds of 0.098 with $p = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05 the significance level for the study. The findings indicate that one unit change in management increases the log odds of sustainability by 0.098. This is in line with study carried out by Chepkonga (2006) who found that principals need training in very key management areas, while Kilonzi (2007) found that most head teachers in primary schools needed training on management. According to Kuria and Onyango (2007), the BoM is not giving the necessary leadership to promote high standards on management in schools.

The study further shows that incentives are significantly associated with sustainability of public day schools with log odds of 0.077. This means that one unit increase in salary increases the log odds by 0.077 with $p = 0.037 < 0.05$ the significance level. The findings are in line with Sprinkle (2,000), who found that incentives have positive effects on performance. According to Armstrong (2000), organizations can use rewards like providing transport fee to increase performance hence increasing sustainability of organizations. The results further show that training and development is not significantly associated with sustainability of day secondary schools. The findings indicate that most of the teachers in day secondary schools are professionally trained teachers.

The results from the table show a logistic regression function:

$$Z = -4.686 + .201X_1 + .098X_2 + .077X_3$$

Where X_1 represent salary, X_2 represent management leadership and X_3 represent incentives while -4.686 represent the y intercept.

7. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1 Summary

The study found that there was a strong positive correlation between salary and sustainability of public day secondary schools as indicated by the beta coefficient of .201 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, we support the directional hypothesis that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between salary and sustainability of day schools. The results indicate increase in salary increases sustainability of day secondary schools. The study found that teachers need to be remunerated commensurate to the work they do. On managerial leadership, the researcher established a positive relationship with sustainability of day schools. A beta coefficient of 0.098 was established at 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicate that an increase in one unit of leadership increases log odds of sustainability by 0.098. The results indicate that there is a need to train the BoM on management skills.

The study further established a significant positive relationship between incentives and sustainability of public day secondary schools. The findings indicates that introduction of incentives raises the motivation of teachers resulting in improved performance. An increase in one unit of incentive raises the log odds of sustainability by 0.077. There the positive hypothesis is accepted. Finally, the researcher established that there was no significant positive relationship between training and development and sustainability of public day secondary schools at 0.05 level of significance. However, it was noted there is a need for teachers to constantly undergo short duration courses to improve their knowledge and skills.

7.2 Conclusion

Free day secondary education will be sustainable with employment adequate and qualified teachers who well remunerated. This is in agreement with the recent signing of collective salary bargaining agreement between the government and the teachers' trade unions (KNUT, 2016). The BoM need to undergo training to equip themselves with managerial skills and improve their managerial abilities. This is because managerial leadership has been found to play a significant role in the growth of schools in particular and increasing enrollment in general BoM contributes to enrolment by

sensitizing the community the community to enroll their children in schools, making good management policies and developing and implementation strategic growth plans. This is supported by Khamati (2013) who arrived at the same findings in his studies on factors influencing implementation of free secondary education in Mumias district. Further the BoM need to come up with a reward system to motivate teachers to improve their performance and meet set targets. This finding is supported by Al-Nsour (2012) who in his studies on the relationship between incentives and organizational performance for employees in Jordanian Universities found there is significant relationship between incentives and performance. Finally policies for training and development of teachers need to be put in place, although it may be costly initially eventually the benefits in terms of performance will out way the cost. The quality of the teachers and their development through training is a major factor in determining the sustainability of day schools. Therefore, there is a need to invest in the development of their skills to increase their productivity. According to Luthern, (2008) the benefits that small organizations receive from training includes increased productivity, low turnover and decreased need for supervision, hence the importance of training and development of teachers for long term sustainability of day secondary schools.

7.3 Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

- The government design pay levels and pay structures that motivate teachers to work and perform at high levels and encourage them to put the same effort in all schools irrespective of the scarcity of resources in these schools.
- The study recommends the training of BoM on management skills to improve the managerial competence and holding consultation with the teaching staff before making sessions that concerns the welfare of teachers.
- There is needed to come up with a reward system that pays a bonus to all the teachers after achieving the set goals.
- The study recommends regular training of teacher in short duration courses like workshops and seminars.

References

1. Aboka, M. (2008): *Free Secondary Education Challenges*; [Paper for KESI Course]; Tom Mboya Labour College, Kisumu, Kenya. Former Deputy PDE, Nyanza.

2. Armstrong, M. (2000) *Strategic Human Resource Management: A Guide to Action*, 2nd Edition. London: Kogan Page.
3. Armstrong, M. (2009). *Armstrong Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. 11th Edition, Kogan Page Limited, London.
4. Assaf, A. (1999). *Managerial Behavior in Contemporary Organizations*. Amman: Dar Zahran.
5. Bandura, A. (1986). *Social Foundation of Thought and Action: A Social Cognitive Theory*. New Jersey: Prentice- Hal
6. Barron, J. M., Berger, M. C., & Black, D. A. (1997). *Employer Search, Training, and Vacancy Duration*. *Economic inquiry*, 35(1), 167-192.
7. Bartel, A. P. (1994). *Productivity Gains from the Implementation of Employee Training Programs*. *Industrial Relations: a Journal of Economy and Society*, 33(4), 411-425.
8. Beardwell, I. and Holden, L. (2001). *Human Resource management: A Contemporary Approach*. Essex: Pearson Education.
9. Beck, G. S. (2004). *Human Capital*. New York: National Bureau of Economic Research.
10. Becker, B. (1996) 'The Impact of Human Resource Management in Organization Performance: Progress and Prospects', *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol 39, pp.779-801.
11. Behrend, T. S., Baker, B. A., & Thompson, L. F. (2009, September). *Effects of Pro-Environmental Recruiting Messages: The role of Organizational Reputations*. *Journal of Business and Psychology*. Retrieved July 1, 2010.
12. Chabari, E. B., (2010). *Challenges Facing Effective Implementation of Free Secondary Education in Public Secondary Schools in Kangundo District, Kenya*. Unpublished Thesis. Chuka University.
13. Chepkonga, S. (2006). *Training Needs Assessment in Financial Management of Secondary School Head Teachers: A Case Study of Nandi North District*, M. Ed Thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya.
14. Chemwei, B. and Koech, S. J. (2015) *Hygiene Related Factors that Influence Teacher Turnover in Public Secondary Schools in Baringo District Kenya*: *Advances in Social Science Research Journal*. Vol.2 No.3
15. Chung, K. H. (1968). *Developing a Comprehensive Model of Motivation and Performance*. *Academy of management journal*, 11(1), 63-73.
16. Cole, G. A. (2002). *Personnel and Human Resource Development*. 5th Edition, York Publishers, Continuum London.

17. Collings, D. G., & Wood, G. (2009). *Human Resource Management: A Critical Approach*. In D. G. Collings & G. Wood (Eds.), *Human Resource Management: A critical Approach* (pp. 1-16). London: Routledge.
18. Cresswell, J. W. (1994). *Research Design: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. California: SAGE Publications, Inc.
19. Cronbach, L. J., (1951) *Coefficient Alpha and the Internal Structure of the Test*. *Psychometric*. 16(3): 297-334.
20. Derek Torrington. (2005). *Human Resource Management, 6th ed*. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall
21. Droar, D. (2006). *Expectancy Theory of Motivation*. Retrieved October 2, 2010, from http://www.arrod.co.uk/archive/concept_vroom.php.
22. Gary Dessler. (2005). *Human Resource Management, 10th ed*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education
23. Gary Desler. (2007) *Human Resource Management, Ninth Edition*. Prentice Hall
24. Guest, D. (2007) *Human Resource Management and the Worker: towards a new Psychological Contract* Oxford University Press.
25. Githuathi, J. N. (2012) *Human Resource Factors Influencing Pupils Performance in Kenya Certificate of primary Education in Thika West District*, Master's Thesis Kenyatta University
26. Gordad, J. (2004) *A Critical Assessment of High Performance Paradigm*, *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, Vol, No2 pp.349-78.
27. Gordon, B. (1992). *Are Canadian Firms Under Investing in Training?* *Canadian Business Economics* 1, 1 25-33.
28. Green, F. (2005) *'Why is work Effort Becoming More Intense?'* *Industrial Relations*
29. Guerrero, Andersen, and Afifi. (2007). *Close Encounters: Communication in Relationships*, 2nd edition. Sage Publications, Inc.
30. Hatch, Mary, J. O. (1997) *Organization Theory* .Oxford University Press Inc. University Press
31. Hayes, J. (2014). *Theory and Practice of Change Management*. London: Palgrave MacMillan.p.137. ISBN 978-1-137-27534-9.
32. Herzberg, Frederick; Mausner, Bernard; Snyderman, Barbara B. (1959). *The Motivation to Work* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley. [ISBN 0471373893](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118133893).
33. Herzberg, Frederick (1966). *Work and the Nature of Man*. Cleveland: World Publishing.
34. Herzberg, Frederick (January–February 1964). "The Motivation-Hygiene Concept and Problems of Manpower"

35. Herzberg, Frederick (January–February 1968). ["One More Time: How Do You Motivate"](#). Harvard Business Review 46 (1): 53–62.
36. Hosmer, D. W. & Lemeshow, S. (2000). Applied Logistic regression (2nd Edition). New York: Wiley.
37. Huseman, R. C., Hatfield, J.D. & Miles, E.W. (1987). *A New Perspective on Equity Theory: The Equity Sensitivity Construct*. The Academy of Management Review. 12; 2: 222-234.
38. Hyun, S. (2009). [Re-examination of Herzberg Two Factor Theory in Food Service \(MS thesis\). Iowa State University.](#)
39. Johnson Controls. (2010). *Global Workplace Solutions Generation Y and the Workplace Annual Report*. Retrieved September 1, 2010.
40. Khamati, J. M. (2013). *Factors influencing Implementation of Free Secondary Education in Mumias District, Kenya*. M.Ed Thesis Maasai University.
41. Kandula. R. S. (2004). *Strategic Human Resource Development*. New Delhi, India: Prentice Hall
42. Kathuri, N. J. (1993). *Introduction to Educational Research*. Egerton: Egerton University Education Book Series.
43. Kinicki, A. & Kreitner, R. (2007). *Organizational Behavior* New York .McGraw Hill.
44. Kilemi, M & Osita, O. (1999): "Public Expenditure and Delivery of Education in Kenya: Lessons from Secondary Schools". In Cost Sharing in Education and Health; Dar es Salaam, Tema publishers.
45. Kilonzi, P. K. (2007). *An investigation of Head Teachers Related Factors affecting the Implementation of Free Primary Education in Yathui Division in Machakos District*; M.Ed Thesis, University of Nairobi.
46. Klerck, G. (2009). *"Industrial Relations and Human Resource Management"*. London: Routledge
47. Kombo K. & Tromp A (2006); *Proposal and Thesis Writing*; Nairobi, Pauline Publications
48. Kraak, A. (2005). Human Resources development and the Skills Crisis in South Africa; The Need for Multi-Pronged Strategy. Journal of education and work 18, 1 57-83.
49. Kreitner, R. and Kinicki, A. (2007). *Organization Behavior* .New York. McGraw Hill
50. Kuria, D. & Onyango, G. (2006); 'Total Quality Management in Secondary Schools' In 'QualitAssurance in Education Research', vol.14, issue 4. 339-362.
51. Kristin, L. S., Jason, D. S. and Michelle, K. D. (2008). "Merit Pay Raises and Organization-Based Self-Esteem," Journal of Organization Behavior, Vol29, No7 pp.967-980.

52. Lawzi, M. (1995). *Motivation and Personality*. New York: Harper
53. Lewin, D. (2003) *Human Resource management and Business performance: Lesson for the 21st Century*, New York.
54. Levacic, R. (1995); *Local Management of Schools: Analysis and Practice*; Buckingham, Oxford University press. Luthan, F.(2008).*Organizational Behavior*. New York McGraw Hill
55. Malik, P. (2009). *Connecting inner power with global change*. Sage Publications.
56. McDonald, D. (2014). *The Firm: The Story of McKinsey and its Secret Influence on American Business*. ISBN 978-1-4391-9098-2.
57. McNamara, C. (2008). *Employee Training and Development; Reasons and Benefits*. Accessed through <http://www.managementhelp.org/index.html>.
58. Messick, D. & Cook, K. (1983). *Equity theory: psychological and sociological Perspectives*. Praeger.
59. McGregor, D. (1960). *The Human Side of Enterprise*, New York, McGraw-Hill.
60. Mondy, R.W. (2005) *Human Resource Management, 9th ed*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
61. Mugenda, O. M. and Mugenda, A. G. (1999). *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: Acts Press
62. Mugenda, O. M. and Mugenda, A.G (2003), *Research Methods*: Nairobi Laba Graphics Services
63. Murrell K. L. and Mimi Meredith (2000) *Empowering Employees*. Illinois: McGraw-Hill-Irwin
64. Nathan, K. (1970). "Clarification and Evaluation of the Two-Factor Theory of Job Satisfaction". Psychological Bulletin.
65. Nunally, J. C. (1978). *Assessment of Reliability in Psychometric Theory*. (2nd Edition). New York: McGraw-Hill
66. Oketch, M. O. and Rolleston, C.M. (2007) *Policies on Free Primary and Secondary Education in East Africa: A review of the Literature*. London: CREATE Pathways to Access Research Monograph, No10. London: Institute of Education.
67. Okumbe J. A. (1998); *Education Management Theory and Practice*, Nairobi, University of Nairobi Press.
68. Oliver, R. (August, 1974). *Expectancy is the probability that the individual assigns to work effort being followed by a given level of achieved task performance*. Expectancy Theory Predictions of Salesmen's Performance. *Journal of Marketing Research* 11, 243-253.
69. Onen, D. (2007). *The Management and Internal Efficiency of Private secondary schools in Uganda*. Unpublished doctoral Thesis, Makerere University Kampala.

70. Onyango A.O. (2006). *Free at last the Government Introduces Free Secondary, Education*, Elimu News Vol.3, 10-13.
71. Orodho, J. A. (2009). *Elements of education and social science research methods*. Maseno: Knezia publishers.
72. Orodho, J. A. (2002). *Techniques of Writing Research Proposals and Reports in Education and Social Sciences*. Nairobi: Masola Publishers.
73. Orpen, C. (1999). *The influence of the training Environment on Trainee Motivation and Perceived Training Quality*. International Journal of Training and Development, 3(1), 34-43.
74. Ostroff, C. & Bowen, D. E. (2004). *Understanding HRM-firm Performance Linkages: the role of the "Strength" of the HRM system*. Academy of Management Review, 29(2), 203-221.
75. Patience, H. (1973). *Organizational Behavior*, Financial Times
76. Pattanayak, B. (2003). *Human Resource Management*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall
77. Pavlov, I. P. (1928). *Lecturers on Conditional Reflexes: Twenty five years of objective Study of higher Nervous activity*, Vol 1, W. H. Grant. New York International Publishers.
78. Republic of Kenya, (2005). *Sessional Paper No. 1 of 2005 on a Policy Framework for Education, Training and Research*. Nairobi: Government Printer
79. Republic of Kenya, (2014). *Sessional Paper No. 1 of 2014 on a Policy Framework for Education, Training and Research*. Nairobi: Government Printer.
80. Richard et al. (2009): *Measuring Organization Performance: Towards methodological Best Practice*. Journal of Management.
81. Robbins, S. (2002). *Organization Behavior*. Asoke K. Gosh, Prentice Hall New Delhi.
82. Robin, S. P. (2003). *Organizational Theory*: New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
83. Sahin, F. (2012). "The mediating effect of leader-member exchange on the relationship between Theory X and Y management styles and effective commitment: A multilevel analysis." Journal of Management and Organization.
84. Scots, S. (2007) *Human Resource Management*. Australia: Thomson
85. Shaun, T. (2006) *Essentials of Human Resource Management*, 5th ed. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
86. Skinner, B. F. (1981). *Selection by Consequences*. Science, American Psychological Association.
87. Skinner, B. F. (1990). *Can psychology be a science of mind?* American Psychologist, 45, 1206-1210.

88. Spector, P.E. (2008). *Industrial and Organizational Behavior* (5th Ed.). Wiley: Hoboken, NJ.
89. Sprinkle, H. (2000), *Applied Project Management: Best Practices on Implementation*. New York: John Wiley & Sons
90. Stredwick Jonn. (2005). *An introduction to Human Resource Management*, 2nd Ed. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
91. Tomioka, M., & Braun, K. L. (2014). Examining Sustainability Factors for Organizations that Adopted Stanford's chronic Disease Self-Management Program. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 2.
92. Towers, David. "[Human Resource Management Essays](#)". Retrieved 2007-10-17
93. Trivedi P. (2006). *Performance Contract Evaluation*: published by in void Bank & Printed in New York.
94. Traupmann, J. (1978). *A longitudinal study of equity in intimate relationships*. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, University of Wisconsin.
95. UNESCO (2005). *Challenges of implementing free primary education in Kenya: Assessment Report. Kenya*. Nairobi: Ministry of Education, Science & Technology.
96. UNESCO (2008). *EFA Global Monitoring Report. Overcoming Inequality: why Governance Matter*. Paris: UNESCO.
97. UNICEF, (2014). *Governance, Management, and Accountability in Secondary Education in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.
98. Upadhaya, B., Munir, R., and Blount, Y. (2014). Association between Performance Measurement Systems and Organizational Effectiveness. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 34(7),2-2.
99. Walster, E., Walster G.W. & Bershcheid, E. (1978). *Equity: Theory and Research*. Allyn and Bacon, Inc.
100. Wanyonyi, G. W. (2004). A Study on Factors Affecting Implementation of Free Primary Education in Nairobi Province, M. Ed Thesis, University of Nairobi.
101. World Bank, (2005). *Brunt Land Commission Report Analysis*. World Bank Press: New York
102. World Bank (2005) *Expanding Opportunities and Building Competencies for Young People: A New Agenda for Secondary Education*. Washington DC: World Bank.
103. World Bank (2008) *Recruiting, Retaining and Retraining Secondary School Teachers and Principals in Sub-Sahara Africa Working Paper No.99*. Washington, D.C, World Bank.

104. Wright, P. & Geroy, D. G. (2001). Changing the Mind set: The Training Myth and the Need For world class Performance. *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 12, 4 586-600.
105. Verma, S., Dewe, P. (2004), *Valuing human resources*, ACCA Report.

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